

The role of Occupational Therapy in promoting occupational engagement and participation in Australian women with PTSD from sexual assault.

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Executive

Summary:

According to data from the Australian Bureau of Statistics reveals a record high in reported sexual assaults across the nation (2023). Experts suggest that a staggering 87% of sexual assault incidents go unreported, indicating a significantly higher undisclosed figure. A meta-analysis in 2023 by Dworkin et al. found that one month after the assault, 75% of women experienced symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). PTSD resulting from sexual assault profoundly disrupts daily functioning, impacting engagement, participation, and overall quality of life. The absence of research and studies on the role of occupational therapists in assisting women with PTSD from sexual assault underscores a significant gap in understanding and addressing the needs of this population. This dearth of literature highlights

the urgency for further exploration and development of tailored occupational therapy interventions to support victims in their recovery journey effectively. This report explores the role occupational therapy has in enhancing engagement and participation in Australian Women with PTSD resulting from sexual assault. It investigates the symptoms women with PTSD usually experience after the trauma and how these symptoms impact their ability to participate and engage in their work, rebuild and maintain their social relationships with people around them, and their ability to engage and participate in their intimate relationship. Interventions primarily used by Occupational Therapists treating this population group are outlined, including methods of Cognitive Behaviour Therapy, Psychoeducation and Sensory and Somatic based approaches. The final chapter identifies personal and environmental barriers to reporting and help-seeking, for females who experience sexual assault in a university setting. Findings demonstrate barriers, such as emotional difficulties that develop as a result of sexual assault, as well as unsuitable university reporting procedures and support services, behave as barriers to seeking out help. In order to reduce the risk of PTSD development, university policies and procedures must better address the needs of students who experience sexual assault. Using a preventative approach, the occupational therapist could educate university staff and students about risks of developing PTSD and ways to help prevent it. This report brings attention to the dire need for more research to be completed in regards to the role of an Occupational Therapist in supporting Australian women with PTSD from sexual assault.

Chapter

1

Prevalence of PTSD and Occupational Therapy Engagement and Participation Among Australian Women Following Sexual Assault

1.1 Introduction

Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) is a debilitating condition that affects individuals who experienced or have witnessed traumatic events (Lancaster et al., 2016). Amongst woman in Australia, sexual assault (SA) is a significant precursor to PTSD, causing severe psychological and physical distress, which may differ by trauma type (Sexual violence, 2024). The ramifications of PTSD extend into various aspects of ones' life, consequently impacting occupational engagement and participation (Davidson, 2000). PTSD following SA has a significant impact on the individual's psychological well-being and greatly hinders their occupational engagement and participation.

Occupational Therapy plays a pivotal and critical role in promoting recovery and facilitating these women's reintegration into meaningful activities (Froehlich, 1992). It focuses on allowing individuals to engage in activities that are meaningful, which is critical for their general well-being (Froehlich, 1992). It helps create tailored interventions that address both the psychological and physical barriers hindering their participation in everyday life (Froehlich, 1992).

The purpose of this chapter is to investigate the prevalence and the biopsychosocial effects of PTSD among Australian woman who have experienced SA and the extent to which these women engage with occupational therapy services.

Understanding the prevalence and the biopsychosocial effects of PTSD and the utilisation of occupational therapy among this demographic is essential for developing effective support systems and intervention strategies (Wafa et al., 2019). With this understanding, healthcare providers, policymakers, and society can endeavor to create a more supportive environment that promotes recovery and resilience in woman affected by such profound trauma.

This chapter will aim to examine the common barriers they confront in pursuing meaningful careers and participating in their daily lives. This chapter will also examine several critical topics in order to have a better understanding of PTSD and occupational therapy engagement and participation among Australian women who have been SA. These questions include:

- How many women with PTSD following sexual assault seek occupational therapy interventions?
- What is the percentage of woman engaging in meaningful occupations despite their sexual assault?
- What are the common barriers that woman face to occupational engagement and participation?

By answering these questions, this chapter provides a comprehensive and detailed overview of the existing situation and identifies gaps in services that need to be addressed.

This chapter will examine these topics by using a variety of data sources, including statistics, research studies, and personal experiences from healthcare providers and survivors. This multifaceted approach seeks to give a holistic understanding of the issue and inform the development of targeted interventions to support occupational engagement and participation amongst women with PTSD followed by SA.

1.2 Magnitude of the issue

The prevalence of PTSD in Australian woman who experienced SA is a major public health concern and remains a deeply troubling issue. SA is a widespread problem that can lead to severe psychological trauma, with lasting impacts on the victim's mental health and wellbeing (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2020 – 2022). One in five women has suffered from sexual violence since the age of 15. Of these women, more than 50% developed PTSD (Sexual Violence, 2024)

Data from the Australian Institute Family Studies (2024) suggest that sexual assault survivors are more likely to acquire PTSD than other trauma survivors.

Despite the high prevalence, less than 30% of these women seek occupational therapy interventions due to barriers such as stigma, and a lack of awareness and limited health care services, demonstrating a significant lack of referral pathways and awareness regarding the benefits of such. Enhanced training for healthcare providers, community education to reduce stigma, and improved referral channels are all critical steps towards closing these gaps. Addressing these barriers can help survivors regain their lives, emphasising on the critical need for an integrated approach to mental health care (Sebesto et al., 2021; Australian Institute of Health and Welfare, 2022).

The impact of PTSD on these women are significantly profound. It affects their ability to pursue meaningful occupations, maintain employment, further their education and participate in social and community activities (Wadsworth, 2019). SA trauma can cause a vicious cycle of withdrawal, further exacerbating mental health issues and diminishing quality of life.

1.3 Occupational engagement and participation

Occupational engagement and participation refer to an individual's involvement in meaningful and purposeful activities that enhance their general well-being and sense of identity (Black et al., 2019). For woman with PTSD followed by SA, engaging in these activities can be challenging due to the prevalent influence of trauma on their mental and physical health (Darroch et al., 2020). Despite the significant hurdles, many of these women maintain participation in meaningful occupations. However, the percentage of women who participate in these activities varies greatly depending on the intensity of their PTSD symptoms, the support systems available to them, and their availability to therapeutic interventions. Roughly 40-60% of women with PTSD following SA can engage in some type of meaningful occupation, but at a lower capacity than before the incident (Isaac et al., 2023). In Australia, the impact of PTSD on women following SA is extremely severe and multifaceted, impacting multiple aspects of occupational engagement and participation.

Symptoms such as hypervigilance, difficulty concentrating, and emotional dysregulation can make it difficult to work. Consequently, these symptoms may result in frequent absenteeism, reduced productivity, and strained relationships with coworkers and managers (Wadsworth et al. 2019). Additionally, the stigma associated with mental health conditions can further exacerbate these challenges, leading to discrimination and isolation in the workplace (Wadsworth et al., 2019).

Women with PTSD followed by SA often neglect personal hygiene, nutrition, and other aspects of self-care due to depressive symptoms, lack of motivation, and overwhelming anxiety (Sexual Assault Support Services, 2024).

The effects of PTSD on social relationships are severe. Woman with PTSD may withdraw from friends and family, resulting in social isolation (Oberoi et al., 2020). Hypervigilance and trust difficulties are frequent in PTSD and can make it difficult to build or sustain strong relationships (Oberoi et al., 2020).

Women with PTSD from SA often find it difficult to participate in leisure activities, which are a typical source of enjoyment and relaxation (O'Doherty et al., 2023). This is typically due to fear, anxiety, or triggers associated with past trauma (O'Doherty et al., 2023).

There are several factors that are impact women with PTSD after SA in engaging in meaningful employment. For example, having adequate access to mental health care services and therapeutic interventions are critical for helping them reclaim their lives. Occupational therapists have been educated to recognise and address the unique barriers

that people with PTSD have, developing therapies to improve their capacity to participate in personally meaningful activities that help them recover.

Occupational therapy interventions for this population focus on restoring and recovering functional abilities, developing coping mechanisms, and encouraging adaptive responses to daily obstacles. These interventions may involve stress management techniques, cognitive-behavioural tactics, and gradual exposure to the triggers in a safe environment (Torchalla, 2018). This inevitability empowers these women to develop and utilise these skills, allowing them to regain a sense of control over their lives (Torchalla, 2018).

Furthermore, occupational therapy adopts a holistic approach to the individuals physical, emotional, cognitive and social well-being. This comprehensive and broad viewpoint is essential in addressing the interconnectedness of PTSD symptoms and their influence on everyday functioning.

1.4 Link to Occupational therapy

Occupational therapy plays a critical role in supporting women with PTSD following SA. Occupational therapy interventions aim to help people engage in meaningful activities, which improves their overall quality of life and facilitating recovery from trauma (Edgelow et al., 2019). For women with PTSD, occupational therapist work to address the psychological and physical hurdles that hinder their participation in daily activities (Eklund, 2021). These occupational therapy interventions are tailored and adapted to each women's individual needs, considering her specific challenges and goals. Therapists use a variety of techniques to assist women with managing PTSD symptoms, developing coping mechanisms, and progressively re-engaging in meaningful occupations (Rocamora – Montengro et al., 2021). Cognitive-behavioural treatments, sensory integration techniques, and mindfulness practices are all intended to reduce anxiety and promote a sense of safety and control (Rocamora – Montengro et al., 2021).

One of the key roles occupational therapy plays is to assist in the reconstruction of routines and structures that are frequently disturbed by PTSD. Occupational therapist assists women establish consistent daily routines, promoting stability and predictability, both of which are crucial elements for recovery (Rocamora – Montengro et al., 2021). This can include activities such as planning and scheduling, breaking down work into small chunks, and gradually increasing task complexity as confidence and competence grow (Rocamora – Montengro et al., 2021). Furthermore, occupational therapy addresses the physical aspects of PTSD. Women who have been sexually assaulted frequently report medical symptoms such as chronic pain, fatigue, and sleep difficulties. Occupational therapist will utilise strategies to manage these symptoms, such as ergonomic adaptations, energy conservation techniques, and relaxation exercises.

By using such measures, it helps these women reduce physical discomfort, and improve their capacity to participate in daily activities as a result (Omura et al., 2021). Another significant aspect of occupational therapy is the focus it has on social participation. Occupational therapist can help women enhance their social skills, form supporting networks, and become more involved in community activities (Cowen et al., 2024). Some examples that this can happen is role-playing social interactions, facilitating support groups, and connecting them to community resources. By doing this, it aims to alleviate isolation and develop a sense of belonging and support (Cowen et al., 2024).

1.5 Rationale for Occupational Therapy Intervention

The rationale for occupational therapy interventions in women with PTSD followed by SA is grounded on the concept that meaningful engagement and participation in daily activities is integral to mental health and well-being (Wadsworth et al., 2019). Occupational therapy addresses the multifaceted impact on PTSD, providing a comprehensive, holistic and client-centred approach, ultimately promoting recovery and resilience (Hammell, 2013).

Addressing the prevalence of OTSD in this population through occupational therapy is essential for several reasons.

A primary reason for using occupational therapy in the treatment of PTSD is its emphasis on functional results. Occupational therapy aims to enhance individuals' ability to perform daily tasks and participate in meaningful activities, making this therapeutic approach more effective than others (Torchalla, 2018).

This functional improvement is essential for women with PTSD as it affects their quality of life and ability to reintegrate into their communities (Torchalla, 2018).

Occupational therapy provides a strength-based approach to recovery by identifying and building on each woman's strength and interest, thereby empowering them to take an active role in their recovery (Hammell, 2013).

Furthermore, because of its flexibility and ability to personalise interventions to best suit their client, occupational therapy is an essential component for recovery for women with PTSD followed by SA as this approach boosts engagement and motivation, thereby resulting in greater outcomes (Hammell, 2018). Additionally, occupational therapy has been shown to be effective in improving outcomes and quality of life for individuals with PTSD (Ertelt, 2023). According to studies, occupational therapy interventions can lead to significant decreases in PTSD symptoms, improvements in occupational performance, and improved overall well-being (Ertelt, 2023).

This indicates the necessity of incorporating occupational therapy into a comprehensive treatment plan for women with PTSD as a result from SA.

1.6 Integration with Project Focus

The aim of this project is to explore the role occupational therapy has in improving occupational engagement and participation among Australian women living with PTSD as a result from SA.

Integrating the findings from the preceding sections provides a more complete and comprehensive understanding of the issues and emphasizes the importance of occupational therapy in this context.

The magnitude of the issue highlights the crucial need for focused interventions. With a significant number of women in Australia experiencing PTSD from SA, and many of them facing barriers to occupational engagement and participation, there is a clear and urgent need for effective therapeutic solutions. The project seeks to close this gap by concentrating on the potential of occupational therapy to support these women.

The exploration of occupational therapy engagement and participation sheds light into the challenges and barriers that are faced by many women with PTSD. Understanding these constraints is critical for developing interventions that are effective, accessible and relevant. This project aims to identify these barriers and propose solutions that occupational therapist can implement to enhance engagement and participation.

The link to occupational therapy emphasises this profession's distinct contributions to the rehabilitation process. The holistic, client-centered, and functional approach of occupational therapy aligns well with the needs of women with PTSD. This project aims to demonstrate the benefits of occupational therapy and how it helps with both psychological and physical aspects of PTSD, facilitating recovery and improving quality of life.

The rationale for occupational therapy interventions reinforces the project's aims by emphasising the evidence-based benefits of this approach. Occupational therapy is an effective and successful approach, especially for women with PTSD due to its emphasises on functional outcomes, strength-based care, and individualised interventions. This project aims to expand on this rationale by giving concrete examples to illustrate the impact of occupational therapy.

1.7 Conclusion

This chapter has looked at the profound impact of PTSD on Australian women who have been sexually assaulted, and the crucial function of occupational therapy in supporting their occupational engagement and participation. Given the high prevalence of PTSD among

women, the need for targeted, effective interventions is evident. Occupational therapy provides a holistic and client-centered approach that tackles both the psychological and physical barriers to effective participation in daily activities. It not only helps women to empower women to reclaim control over their lives by concentrating on functional outcomes but enhances their overall well-being and quality of life.

By understanding the prevalence and biopsychosocial effects of PTSD in this population, it highlights the significance of integrating occupational therapy in comprehensive treatment plans. This approach helps facilitate recovery and promotes resilience and social reintegration. By addressing the multifaceted impacts of PTSD, occupational therapy supports women in overcoming barriers to occupational engagement and participation, creating a supportive environment for their recovery journey.

This project highlights the critical importance of occupational therapy in assisting Australian women with PTSD because of SA, emphasising the need for enhanced awareness, accessibility, and integration of these services to promote recovery and resilience.

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Chapter

2

How does PTSD caused by sexual assault impact the occupational engagement and participation of Australian women with PTSD in multiple areas of their lives?

2.1 Introduction

It is very common for Australian women to encounter different types of unwanted sexual experiences with research showing that approximately 2 million Australian adults experienced sexual assault at least once in their life (Healthdirect, 2023). Among these people, more than 85% of victims who experienced sexual assault were female in Australia (Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS), 2022). ABS (2022) found something more concerning is that more than 90% of women did not make an official report to the police after being sexually assaulted. Those who experience PTSD after being sexually assaulted have a higher possibility than others to have post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression and anxiety disorders, also they are more likely to experience mood swings (Chopra et al., 2012). Although PTSD could be a temporary response to the traumatic events they experienced, it could also develop into a chronic issue if it is left untreated (O'Donnell et al., 2007). PTSD appears when people experience extreme fear and anxiousness that stays on their mind after a single or several traumatic events which could cause people mental health problems (Healthdirect, 2023). Therefore, this chapter is to delve into how PTSD caused by sexual assault influences different aspects of Australian female victims.

2.2 Method

MEDLINE, CINAHL, Google Scholar, and Cochrane Library are used to search literature that studies sexual assault experienced by women and Australian women with PTSD. This chapter is attempting to focus mainly on adult women who were sexually assaulted by either a stranger, an intimate partner or anyone in any situation. As long as they fulfil two criteria which include participants being Australian women, 18 years old or above, experienced any form of sexual assault in the past and experiencing PTSD symptoms. The systematic review, randomised-controlled trial and meta-analysis are prioritised over other types of research. Keywords used in the search are PTSD, occupational therapy, impact, influence, participation, rape, occupational performance, social isolation, intimate relationships, quality

of life, work performance, PTSD symptoms, posttraumatic stress disorder. MOHO model is also used to explain how PTSD is affecting victims' participation

2.3 What PTSD symptoms do women usually experience after sexual assault?

1 in 5 Australian women have at least experienced a certain type of sexual violence at the age of 15, these experiences could develop into trauma or negative influences on people's health (Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW), 2024). Women who experienced sexual assault were found to have strong negative beliefs and thoughts related to their PTSD symptoms and the event happened which indicates that cognition plays a crucial part in people's experience of PTSD (Shin et al., 2020). To avoid the traumatic memories, the survivors could continue to perform experiential avoidance to avoid their thoughts and the feelings caused by the event to escape from the pain (Tull & Lizabeth, 2003). During their recovery, hyperarousal symptoms are commonly seen in PTSD which include increased aggression, hypervigilance, increased startled reaction, sleep disturbance, and reduced concentration (Zoellner et al., 2000). Although hyperarousal symptoms could quickly appear after victims are assaulted, hyperarousal symptoms might not disappear quickly and can develop into chronic hyperarousal if it is neglected (Kendall-Tackett, 2000). In the long term, the victim can show signs of anxiety, depression, fear or suicidal thoughts (Tarzia, 2020). Besides, women with this trauma can have freezing, flashbacks and nightmares related to their traumatic experience (Yang et al., 2023). More than 80% of women after sexual assault have developed a high level of depressive symptoms (Abrahams et al., 2013). They could also present self-blame, negative thoughts, and denial of the event after the assault (Harris et al., 2020). Victims who had these experiences might sustain a long period of self-shame (Amstadter & Vernon, 2008). The self-blame can be worse when the environment they are in does not support them or even blame them for the assault (Moor & Farchi, 2011). Besides emotional damage, victims can also go through other impacts. Victims may find it difficult to enjoy sexual activities due to their trouble with sexual arousal or the lack of sexual interest (Ellis, 1981). Victims who experienced sexual assault might experience different mental illnesses including insomnia, eating disorders, mood disorders, and PTSD (World Health Organization (WHO), 2013). Although PTSD could be temporary for some, those who were physically attacked during the event, with little self-esteem, and constant fear of being in a group of people, and constant fear are more likely to experience chronic PTSD (Darves-Bornoz et al., 1998).

In some cases, the PTSD symptoms could worsen due to victims using unhealthy ways to escape pain. Sexual violence could potentially lead to a higher possibility of alcohol consumption (Devries et al., 2013). It is common for women who experience sexual assault to consume alcohol or even drugs to temporarily erase the negative feelings or emotional responses triggered by the event (Hedtke et al., 2008). The use of drugs would not only damage their physical health but could also lead to posttraumatic stress symptoms being more aggressive (Swain et al., 2020).

2.4 How does PTSD caused by sexual assault affect the work performance and participation of Australian women in the workplace?

Sexual violence could lead to physical and mental illnesses that adversely impact the survivor's employment, economic stability, and ability to return to their normal life and relationships (AIHW, 2024). These negative events have huge detrimental impacts on victims' careers (Adams et al., 2012). Instead of reporting the assault, most Australian women were found to avoid going to work after the event (Birinxhikaj & Guggisberg, 2017). The MOHO model explained that psychological difficulties could affect a person's volition to engage in meaningful activities which include working (Harel-Katz & Carmeli, 2019).¹ in 4 victims mentioned that they have taken time off from their work temporarily, or even left their jobs to avoid being assaulted again (AIHW, 2024; Respect@Work, n.d.). This could be due to victims attempting to avoid interaction with other people, thinking they are not worthy, or doubting their own identity (Boyd, 2011). They might not only take time off from their work but also experience reduced job performance, be unable to work or even lose their job after being assaulted which leads to an economic crisis for them (Loya, 2014). It is because any form of sexual abuse involving verbal, or physical actions could lead to a significant decline in work efficiency and cause negative effects on professional relationships between staff (Tekin & Bulut, 2014). When victims experience hyperarousal symptoms caused by PTSD, they might find it difficult to sleep, concentrate at work, control their aggression, or startle responses (Acierno et al., 2003). Due to being overly alert, victims could be extremely paranoid and become unusually cautious about their safety to avoid sexual assault (Freeman et al., 2013). This will then affect their work performance. The decreased work productivity and performance will further lead to psychological distress and hinder their recovery which is a vicious cycle (Lorenz & O'Callaghan, 2020). While some may withdraw from their work for recovery, others might choose to utilise medication to escape the pain and manage the symptoms caused by the event or their PTSD to continue working on their job duties. It is because Australian women with PTSD is found to be almost 2.5 times and 4.5 times more likely to experience alcohol addiction or drug addiction than people without PTSD (Mills et al.,

2006). In that case, they might choose to use medication to control these symptoms. However, excessive use of medication or drugs is found to cause impaired memory, decreased focus, disturbed sleep, and increased anxiousness or aggression (Tipps et al., 2014). PTSD itself and the severity of the symptoms are found to be highly correlated to whether the victims will experience cravings for drugs or alcohol (Coffey et al., 2002). These would therefore further affect their work performance in their workplace or even cause job loss (Reynolds et al., 2005).

When victims need to request leave from their job, they could feel forced to disclose their traumatic experiences (Lorenz & O'Callaghan, 2020). Negative reactions from other people upon their disclosure could further worsen their PTSD symptoms (Sylaska & Edwards, 2013). Also, their colleagues' negative or positive social reactions could affect their work performance, willingness to go to work, and recovery speed (Lorenz & O'Callaghan, 2020). If their colleagues believe that it is their fault or react in a negative way, the victims might feel even more shameful or embarrassed which stops them from transitioning into their normal life again.

2.5 How does PTSD caused by sexual assault impact Australian women in building and maintaining their social relationships with other people?

The severity of PTSD is found to be associated with the level of social support the victims receive which means their PTSD would be more serious when they receive less social support (Van Stolk-Cooke et al., 2024). Disclosure of their traumatic experience to people around them is a type of informal support that the survivors would need to recover from trauma (Jacques-Tiura et al., 2010). Victims of sexual assaults often receive negative social responses after being assaulted which further accelerates their PTSD symptoms (Ullman & Peter-Hagene, 2016). To avoid this, many of them would choose to not disclose it to people which leads to a lack of social support and eventually slow down their recovery.

Although Australian society is now more accepting of the victims who were sexually assaulted, there are still voices that are not very welcoming to these victims. Until 2021, more than 30% of people believed that women who made a report of being sexually assaulted were only attempting to bring their partner back to themselves (National Community Attitudes towards Violence against Women Survey (NCAS), 2021). Besides, NCAS (2021) also found that more than 20% of people believe that women reported being sexually assaulted only because they regretted their mutually agreed sexual activities. More than 20% of people believe that males committing sexual crimes are inevitable because they are not able to recognise the signs of a woman not wanting to be involved in sexual activities when males

are sexually aroused (NCAS, 2021). These data could be daunting for Australian women to disclose their traumatic experiences to their loved ones because they do not want to be perceived as attention seekers or being dramatic over unimportant issues. 1 in 3 people being sexually assaulted showed unusual levels of stress, reduced trust in other people, low self-worth (Respect@Work, n.d.). Victims with PTSD usually demonstrate impaired social functions when interacting with other people. Negative reactions from other people including blaming the victim or stigma could lead to more severe PTSD symptoms (Littleton, 2011). Survivors with PTSD might have less interest in social activities because they are worried, nervous, and irritable (U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs (USDVA), n.d.). They might also attempt to avoid people with a similar appearance as the perpetrator during social interaction (USDVA, n.d.). As mentioned before, sexual violence could lead to PTSD and depression. Posttraumatic symptoms and depression are found to affect a person's social ability and emotional functions (Ozdemir et al., 2015). Because of that, Australian women found themselves being more detached from people around them and more likely to avoid interaction with other people after being sexually assaulted (Forbes et al., 2013). The increased social isolation could lead to a worse traumatic experience which decreases their ability to seek social support (Pfitzner et al., 2022).

2.6 How does PTSD caused by sexual assault impact Australian women on their engagement and performance in their intimate relationship?

Sexual intimacy is perceived as a crucial part of an intimate relationship that makes both parties feel loved and valued (Zhang, 2022). However, sexual violence could destroy the positivity in a usual intimate experience. PTSD related to sexual assault would usually lead to a decline in their sexual ability and their level of satisfaction (Van & Ensink, 2000). More than 80% of women experience a phobia of sex, a lack of sexual interest, and difficulty with arousal after being assaulted (Becker et al., 1986). The MOHO model explained that a lack of interest in sexual activity could reduce their level of participation (Morrison & Poblete-Almendras, 2023).

Victims could find it difficult to engage in sexual activities after being sexually assaulted because it triggers their PTSD flashbacks in some cases which could reduce their sexual desire for their romantic partner (O'Callaghan et al., 2018). Their trauma not only affects them but also their romantic partner as well. When their romantic partner attempts to support their traumatised partner, the supporter's emotional needs might sometimes be ignored and they might feel trapped in the relationship (O'Callaghan et al., 2018). Also, people who have PTSD could be frequently angry, overly alert, easily shocked, and unable to concentrate which

reduces their functions in maintaining conversations with their partner or even a relationship (Forbes et al., 2018). This could potentially destroy both of their mental well-being.

Sexual violence is something that could be performed by both strangers or people who know the victim including their intimate partner, family members, friends, or even ex-partner (ABS, 2023). However, it causes more psychological harm when it is performed by their intimate partner. The impacts become different as well. 1 in 4 Australian women have experienced sexual violence from their intimate partner since they were teenagers (AIHW, 2024). Sexual violence caused by intimate partners could cause fear, shame, and suicidal thoughts (Bagwell-Gray et al., 2015). Australian women who experienced sexual assault from their partners believe that this unique and catastrophic experience causes more aggressive symptoms than being assaulted by a random stranger which destroys the trust, intimate foundation, and the sense of security they have for a romantic relationship (Tarzia, 2020). Because of these, the victims could find it difficult to rebuild intimate relationships after being assaulted (Oosterhoff et al., 2023).

2.7 Conclusion

PTSD caused by sexual assault could lead to different problems in different aspects of the victim's life. The health problems that PTSD causes could be anxiety, mental fatigue, and insomnia (LEES et al., 2019). The traumatic events could potentially lead to the patient experiencing a higher possibility of drug or alcohol addiction (Ullman et al., 2013). PTSD itself and the use of medication could significantly reduce the patient's concentration, and hypervigilance and accelerate their irritability which could adversely influence their work performance and ability to communicate with their colleagues (Jacobsen et al., 2001). After being sexually assaulted, victims could also experience difficulties in returning to their ordinary social lives because they might attempt to avoid social interaction. Sexual violence could affect the trust and relationship between the victim and their partner. Intimate relationships will be more likely to be affected when the sexual assault is performed by their partner.

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Chapter

3

**Interventions used in Occupational Therapy to support women experiencing
PTSD after sexual assault.**

3.1 Introduction

PTSD is characterised by hyperarousal, avoidance, negative mood, and dissociation (Pagel, 2021). The symptoms of PTSD from sexual assault significantly disrupt a victim's daily functioning, engagement, participation, and overall quality of life as outlined in chapter one and two of this textbook (Chivers-Wilson, 2006; Sareen, 2014; Villalta et al., 2020). The role an Occupational Therapist provides is fundamental in equipping Sexual Assault victims with the tools to address the functional impairments and daily life disruptions that have resulted from the ongoing symptoms of PTSD. Unfortunately, data regarding the interventions used by Occupational Therapists in providing services to this population is limited. This chapter aims to answer the following questions:

- 1. What gaps exist in the current literature regarding the effectiveness and implementation of OT interventions for women experiencing PTSD following sexual assault?**
- 2. What are the primary interventions used by Occupational Therapists working with women with PTSD due to sexual trauma?**
- 3. What are the recommendations for future practitioners working with this population group?**

Available literature was reviewed through a comprehensive search of five databases: PubMed, Cochrane Library, Google Scholar, Medline, and OT Seeker. Most of the studies were conducted in psychology schools and purposed for use by mental health workers. Very few studies met the initial criteria, which included some specifics of sexual assault-related PTSD; therefore, searches were broadened to a generalised PTSD approach by OTs. Current literature predominantly emphasises a multidisciplinary approach, with data highly regarding the effectiveness of psychological interventions such as Cognitive Behavioural Therapy (CBT) and Prolonged Exposure Therapy (PE) as primary treatments for PTSD (Phelps et al., 2022; Mansour et al., 2023; Watkins et al., 2018). Psychologists and Occupational Therapists should work collaboratively with survivors to address both the psychological stress and the functional impairment of PTSD in a holistic way. A trauma-informed care approach and training is highly regarded for practitioners working with this population group.

3.2 Intervention 1: An awareness of PTSD symptomology and exercises to manage them.

Psychoeducation and coping skills

Occupational Therapists can implement psychoeducation and training in coping skills for women with PTSD from sexual assault as an intervention strategy. Psychoeducation relates to all areas that an individual with PTSD would benefit from learning about, including

symptomology, arousal triggers, and occupational impacts that may be common for women who have experienced sexual assault (Bryant-Davis, 2011). This knowledge provides victims with a sense of normalcy and reassurance for what they are experiencing, as well as reduces their feelings of isolation and confusion. Education can bring awareness to and empower the individual to anticipate and manage symptoms of PTSD effectively, as well as help individuals recognise the broader impacts of PTSD and encourage engagement in therapy to address these challenges (Bryant-Davis, 2011; Torchalla et al., 2018). Psychoeducation serves as an initial step for several evidence-based psychological interventions, such as CBT, which we will discuss later in this chapter.

Common coping strategies OTs can teach include mindfulness practices and relaxation techniques, which can be used to reduce emotional dysregulation and stress-inducing symptoms of PTSD.

Mindfulness

Reid (2011) and Elliot (2011), among other scholars, have made a solid theoretical case that mindfulness has a place within the OT scope of practice. Mindfulness-based strategies encourage being present and accepting thoughts and emotions as they come (Boyd et al., 2018; McVeigh, 2015). Evidence suggests mindfulness promotes awareness of the current moment and reduces avoidant behaviours and negative thought patterns like self-blame and shame (Batten et al., 2015; Boyd et al., 2018). These practices are relevant as women with PTSD because of sexual assault are strongly associated with these thought patterns (Kline et al., 2021). Meditation, yoga, or walking can integrate mindfulness, enhance self-awareness of internal and external stimuli, and ultimately assist individuals in acknowledging and managing discomfort (Lang et al., 2012; Folette et al., 2006; Martin, 2005). These skills can be beneficial for managing the symptoms of PTSD and reducing the impact it has on daily occupations.

Relaxation Techniques:

Additionally, relaxation therapy techniques, such as guided imagery, deep breathing, and progressive muscle relaxation, provide therapeutic avenues to reduce tension and anxiety (Norelli et al., 2023). Kumari & Patil's 2023 study found guided imagery effective in minimising anxiety and improving the quality of life of patients with anxiety disorder. Providing

evidence that guided imagery can improve one of the prevalent symptoms of PTSD: anxiety (Bisson et al., 2015). Toussaint et al. 2021 study found a significant statistical improvement in relaxation from methods such as muscle relaxation, deep breathing, and guided imagery for participants compared to the control group. Although this study did not focus on patients with PTSD or, more specifically, women with PTSD from sexual assault, its results are still significant in indicating the benefits of these techniques. Results by Hwan Kim et al. (2013) support the notion that deep breathing exercises significantly reduce PTSD symptoms. Thus, teaching these relaxation techniques are one of many ways an Occupational Therapist can support women with PTSD in managing their symptoms to enable engagement in meaningful occupations.

3.3 Intervention 2: Implementing methods of Cognitive Behaviour Therapy to promote participation.

Cognitive Behaviour Therapy (CBT) has been widely used by many mental health practitioners, including Occupational Therapists, to provide evidence-based psychotherapy that aims to reshape negative thoughts, emotions and behaviours with cognitive restructuring and behaviour modification techniques (Nakao et al., 2021). Occupational Therapists engage in this intervention to assist clients who have discontinued meaningful activities due to negative thought patterns and behaviours of avoidance.

Cognitive Restructuring

Cognitive restructuring teaches clients to identify negative biased cognitive distortions, then to re-interpret or transform them (Curtiss et al., 2021). This technique in CBT has proven effective in reducing PTSD symptoms (Lu et al. 2009; Mueser et al., 2009; Mueser et al., 2015;

Rosenberg et al., 2004). Evidence for women with PTSD from sexual assault is congruent, though very limited for women with PTSD specifically from sexual assault (Jaycox et al., 2002). The literature review found no evidence of Occupational Therapists providing cognitive restructuring for women with PTSD specifically from sexual assault. An Occupational Therapist can provide education and training on how to identify and transform negative thoughts stemming from the sexual trauma. With practice, and in time, it is hypothesised that the victim will reclaim their sense of safety, resilience, and functional capacity to engage in meaningful occupations otherwise disrupted by these cognitive distortions. In this way Occupational Therapists play a significant role in promoting engagement and participation through exercises of cognitive restructuring.

Prolonged Exposure Therapy

Behaviours of avoidance and self-isolation are commonly practiced among people with PTSD (Trochalla et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2023). These behaviours act as a short-term prevention of the processing of the traumatic event, the thought patterns it ignites, and the distress associated with it (Tipsword et al., 2022). However, research indicates that this method, in the long term, contributes to and perpetuates the maintenance of PTSD (Clark, 2000). Avoiding and self-isolating from occupations, environments, or people that may trigger the re-experiencing or remembering of the traumatic event can consequently impact an individual's daily occupations, routines, and habits (Chivers-Wilson, 2006). An effective type of CBT that enables the gradual re-engagement with trauma-induced stressors is Prolonged Exposure Therapy (PE) (Watkins et al., 2018). PE has two main treatment processes; imaginal and in vivo exposures. Occupational Therapists can collaborate with psychologists to systematically confront an individual's feared stimuli; a psychologist may address imaginal exposure while the Occupational Therapist addresses in vivo exposure. For women with PTSD from sexual assault their feared stimuli may differ, and can depend on where the trauma occurred, what elements were involved and who perpetrated it. An Occupational Therapist may discuss these elements, considering what environments and situations are triggering and listing them in a hierarchy from least distressing to most distressing (Trochalla et al., 2018). Working gradually through this list with the use of coping skills and techniques for moments of distress, a victim's anxiety surrounding the stimuli may decrease and eventually diminish. It is important to facilitate this treatment at a slow and manageable pace that does not overload the client. This process, facilitated holistically by trauma informed practitioners can foster a sense of empowerment, resilience, and confidence for victims in managing trauma-induced avoidant behaviours (McLean & Foa, 2011). Ultimately, through PE facilitated by Occupational Therapists, sexual assault victims

can reclaim their occupational roles and participate more fully in activities they value, experiencing reduced symptoms of PTSD and improved overall well-being.

3.4 Intervention 4: An awareness of bodily sensations through somatic and sensory-based exercises.

As previously outlined, PTSD can cause the dysregulation of the central nervous system and cause symptoms of hyperarousal and dissociation. These symptoms can create a disconnect between the mind and the body of a person with PTSD, including women who have experienced sexual assault. To bridge this disconnect, emerging approaches of somatic and sensory based interventions have been facilitated by Occupational Therapists and mental health practitioners (Brooks, 2021).

Sensory Based Interventions

Sensory processing is the umbrella term for the organisation, interpretation and registration of sensory stimuli input received from the senses and transformed into behavioural responses (Passarello et al., 2022). Empirical evidence has found that people with PTSD, experiencing symptoms of excessive emotional dysregulation, hyperarousal, and dissociation, are likely to have difficulties and differences in their ability to interpret sensory stimuli. This is due to the hyposensitivity and hypersensitivity to external stimuli these symptoms as well as the thoughts relating to the trauma can elicit (Harricharan et al., 2021; Lanius et al., 2010; Williamson et al., 2015). This can lead to sensory processing disorders and dysfunction which impact an individual's ability to participate fully and feel safe in daily activities. Women with PTSD due to sexual assault have notably experienced differences in their sensory processing that have impacted their daily functioning (Gerney & Muffly, 2015). Sensory processing integration and modulation are emerging approaches in the occupational therapy scope of practice (McGreevy & Boland, 2020; Wright et al., 2022). The information is limited in how

occupational therapists have specifically helped this population group with PTSD-inducing sensory issues. However, there is evidence that sensory integration with a generalised mixed gender adult population with PTSD has the potential to be effective (McGreevy & Boland, 2020). Sensory interventions aim to reduce hypervigilance, dissociation, and avoidance by providing sensory tools, and adaptive approaches to stimuli that help individuals regulate sensory sensitivities and continue participation in occupations that were otherwise disrupted by these PTSD symptoms. In this way, occupational therapist can play a critical role in promoting engagement and recovery for women with PTSD from sexual assault.

Somatic Therapy Interventions

Preliminary evidence suggests that Somatic Experiencing (SE) is effective in improving PTSD related symptoms, however data was conducted on a wide range of PTSD inducing traumas, and non-specific to Occupational Therapist implementation (Brom et al., 2017; Kuhfub et al., 2021). SE is a body-orientated approach that focuses on the healing of trauma and traumatic stress (Payne et al., 2015). SE theory explains that PTSD symptoms originate from an incomplete initiated psychophysiological defensive reaction, leaving the individual in a permanent overwhelm of the innate central nervous system (Levine, 1997). This leads to the ongoing emotional, sensory, and somatic dysfunction and dysregulation, resulting in hyper and hypo sensitivity that is seen in people with PTSD. SE aims to direct a clients attention inward to sensations of interoception, proprioception and kinaesthesia to regulate their symptoms (Kuhfub et al., 2021). Occupational Therapist can implement SE psychoeducation and exercises with women with PTSD due to sexual assault to promote the mind to body connection, and ultimately, restore their capacity to participate and engage in the tasks that were otherwise disturbed by these psychopathological dysregulations.

3.5 Discussion

The interventions highlighted in this chapter provide insight into the approaches Occupational Therapists can implement when working with women experiencing PTSD following sexual assault. While there is evidence supporting various occupational therapy interventions like Cognitive Behaviour Therapy, Sensory and Somatic based approaches, psychoeducation, and the training of copying skills, across the board, there is a need for more specific studies focusing on their effectiveness specifically in women who have experienced sexual assault.

Existing research often includes mixed-gender populations or broader trauma samples, which may not fully capture the unique needs and responses of women who have experienced sexual assault. Future studies should employ rigorous methodologies, including randomised controlled trials (RCTs) with large sample sizes, to assess the effectiveness of these interventions specifically for this population.

The literature highlights the importance of a multidisciplinary approach to treating PTSD, emphasising the collaboration between psychologists and occupational therapists.

An occupational therapist's unique perspective of holistic client-centred care focused on the re-engagement of occupations and recovery of functional capacity complements a psychologist's focus on psychological rehabilitation. All interventions interlink and come back to the functional impacts that PTSD has on an individual's participation and engagement in everyday occupations.

3.6 Implications

This chapter identified three integral intervention themes used in occupational therapy to assist people with PTSD. It highlights the fundamental role an occupational therapist can provide helping women with PTSD due to sexual assault and acts as a guidance for occupational therapists new to this population group. It is essential that more research is conducted regarding the specific use of these OT interventions with women who have PTSD specifically from sexual assault.

3.7 Recommendations

- Due to the lack of data specifically for occupational therapists regarding this group it is recommended that future researchers consider performing randomised-control-trials and longitudinal studies to increase the data.
- Moving forward each Occupational Therapist should prioritise a person-centered perspective, considering a victim's severity of symptoms, culture and comfortability with regard to the intervention that is implemented (Joseph, 2004).
- Working closely within a multi-disciplinary team is highly recommended. Psychologists, counsellors, or mental health practitioners, all provide different perspectives, and this collaboration is ideal for creating a holistic approach with the client (Trochalla et al., 2018).
- The continuation of professional development, education, and mentorship for Occupational Therapists in working with this population group is crucial to providing the highest quality treatment. Trauma-Informed- Care Training is significant for understanding and promoting the recovery of people with trauma, specifically PTSD (Grossman et al., 2021).

3.8 Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has outlined the primary interventions used among Occupational Therapists working with PTSD victims. Occupational Therapists typically take the role of educating, training, and collaborating with individuals to minimise the symptoms of PTSD and re-engage in occupations that the trauma has impacted. This chapter promotes the collaboration of Occupational Therapists and psychologists in employing CBT and sensory-somatic approaches to holistically address both the psychological and functional impacts of PTSD due to sexual assault. Moving forward, it is important for Occupational Therapists to consider all interventions and to personalise treatments for each individual, considering factors such as symptom severity, culture, environment, and appropriateness of the treatment for the individual. Future studies should focus on evaluating occupational therapy's role and long-term impacts on this specific population group. By increasing the research in this area occupational therapists can better support the recovery of PTSD and support the re-engagement of daily occupations for women who have experienced sexual assault.

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Chapter

4

**The Role of an Occupational Therapist in Supporting University Students at
Risk of Developing PTSD and Occupational Imbalance**

4.1 Introduction

In Australia, a 2022 National Student Safety Survey that included students from 38 Australian university institutions found 1 in every 20 students had been sexually assaulted in an Australian university setting (Heywood et al., 2021, p.1). That is, from the commencement of their university studies. In this study, results indicated females were at a greater risk of experiencing sexual abuse (41.8 %) compared to males (14.1%) (Heywood et al., 2021, p.2), with 1.4 % of female students experiencing sexual abuse, in the previous year, in contrast to their male student counterparts at 0.6% (Heywood et al., 2021, p.34). Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) can develop a result of a traumatic incident, such as sexual abuse. Individuals with PTSD avoid stimuli, such as places, people, or activities that trigger traumatic memories of the sexual assault, and cause distress (Chivers-Wilson, 2006). Studies have shown these behaviours can negatively impact an individual's participation in meaningful occupations, and act as a barrier to maintaining occupational balance and overall health (Potter et al., 2018). With respect to sexual assault, research indicates individuals that receive help from sexual assault support services early may reduce the risk of developing PTSD (Chivers-Wilson, 2006). Despite this, according to a Heywood et al. (2022) study only 1 in 20 students sexually assaulted made a formal complaint to their university (p. 45), with students more commonly seeking help outside of the university setting (Heywood et al., 2022, p. 54). Occupational Therapists have a role in improving health outcomes for those with PTSD, by working with trauma associated functional deficits to support occupational participation (Torchalla et al., 2019). Following sexual assault, by assisting to provide efficient and timely access to support services for this population, Occupational Therapists may help to reduce the likelihood of PTSD development that is a barrier to occupational participation for this population (Chivers-Wilson, 2006). In regards to PTSD, associated with sexual assault, there is a gap in the research for OT intervention, with many studies focusing on male veterans (Anzalone et al., 2022). The purpose of this study is to investigate the current perspectives on personal and environmental barriers to reporting and seeking support services, of women who have experienced sexual assault in a university setting. With this knowledge, Occupational Therapists may help to adapt support service delivery to improve access for women who have been sexually assaulted in a university setting, thereby reducing the risk of PTSD development, and its negative impacts on occupation participation (Torchalla et al., 2018). Furthermore, Occupational Therapists may also improve access to supports for students who already have PTSD a result of sexual assault, and need to restore occupational balance (Anzalone et al., 2022). The question being investigated in this study is, what personal and environmental factors act as barriers to

reporting and seeking support services, for female university students who experience sexual assault in a university setting?

4.2 Methods

A mixed methods approach was adopted using statistical findings from reports and a review of qualitative studies to identify themes. Material included two Australian reports, journal articles from both Australian and non-Australian countries, and an Australian podcast that was included due to high relevance. A limitation of this approach is that not all qualitative data and statistics were based on Australian students attending universities within Australia. Despite this, findings based on Australian content was strengthened when non-Australian articles presented similar themes. The majority of studies included female university students, who had been sexually assaulted in a university setting. Having said this, some articles were more general pertaining to the nature of PTSD and how Occupational Therapy may assist to treat it. Articles used were located via health science databases, such as CINAHL Plus with Full Text. Additional sources were retrieved from journal article references or by conducting searches via google search engine.

4.3.1 Limited Awareness of What Constitutes Sexual Assault

The theme surrounding limited awareness of what constitutes sexual assault was recognised, particularly regarding distinct acts that are identified as sexual assault. According to DeLoveh & Cattaneo (2017), students that labelled the incident as sexual assault were the only individuals that sought out support services. In contrast, those unsure of whether the

sexual assault occurred, often blamed themselves for not preventing the abuse and decided not to report, or did so a significant amount of time later (DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017). In support of this finding, previous studies have shown over sixty percent of women who have been sexually assaulted, according to the legal definition, did not interpret their experience this way (DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017).

4.3.2 Limited Awareness of the University Sexual Assault Reporting Process or Help Services

Various students addressed being unsure of how to complain or report the sexual assault, and were unaware of how this process could assist them (Nisbet et al., 2022, p.26). Regarding the rationale for not making a formal report, 19.6% of students stated being unaware of whom to approach to submit a formal complaint (Heywood et al., 2022, p.47). In a previous study, despite being aware of sexual assault support services, students were less sure about their function and how they could help them (DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017). Similarly, a Holland & Cortina (2017) study showed some students were unaware of available supports and having discovered they existed, believed too much time had passed to report the incident (Holland & Cortina, 2017).

4.4 Lack of Support in the University Sexual Assault Reporting Process

In this theme, students communicated apprehensions regarding the university reporting procedure, and held a belief the university would put their needs before the student's (Nisbet et al., 2022, p.26). Based on a Heywood et al. study(2022), approximately half of students who experienced sexual assault and formally disclosed this to the university, were unsatisfied with the complaints and university reporting procedure. Furthermore, of those who did formally report the incident, 43.7% indicated not being given descriptions of how to report or submit a complaint at university (p.45). Other barriers identified regarding reporting procedures were, lack of procedure transparency, fears the report would not remain confidential (Heywood et al., 2022, p.47), and slow processing times (Nisbet et al., 2022, p. 37). This information was corroborated by reports made by Sharna Bremner, founder of End

Rape on Campus Australia, who stated university complaint processing times are considerable, and often do not offer a complaint outcome (Coote, 2022). To add to this, a number of studies identified the university policies and processes themselves as a barrier to students accessing campus supports (Coote, 2022; Holland & Cortina, 2017).

4.5 Unsuitable Sexual Assault Support Services

According to a Heywood et al., study (2022), 33.8% of students who were sexually assaulted and sought out university support, demonstrated a lack of satisfaction with the level of support received (p. 52). Based on one individual's experience, who resided in student accommodation, student leaders and associated university staff were not coached on the steps to take, following student reports of sexual abuse (Nisbet et al. study, 2022, p.26). In a Holland and Cortina (2017) study, similar student views were shared by university students who also identified housing staff as an inappropriate source of support.

4.6.1 Feelings as Barriers to Reporting Sexual Assault or Seeking Help

This theme focused on feelings reported by students that behaved as barriers to reporting the sexual assault or obtaining help. According to a Heywood et al. (2022) study, some students reported feeling assistance was not required, as well as emotions of shame or embarrassment (Heywood et al., 2022, P. 47; Nisbet et al., 2022, p.26). Feelings of shame and embarrassment a result of sexual assault, were identified in multiple studies (Holland & Cortina, 2017; DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017). A feeling of shame was considered the largest barrier to seeking out help and results from an individual having a negative perception of their identity (Tarzia et al., 2024; DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017). Other feelings, such as fears of being judged or socially stigmatised were also identified in various studies (Holland & Cortina, 2017; Nisbet et al., 2022, p. 26). In a DeLoveh & Cattaneo (2017) study, 10 in 14 participants stated possessing these feelings, while 13 in 14 students anticipated a negative reaction from at least one support service they considered approaching for help. Lastly, self-blame was a re-occurring theme, that impeded the seeking of support services. In one study, 12 in 14 participants blamed themselves for the sexual assault (DeLoveh & Cattaneo,

2017). Reasons for self-blame included, students were drinking alcohol at the time of assault (Holland & Cortina, 2017; Tarzia et al., 2024), or due to alcohol being consumed at the time, was uncertain if they had given consent (Holland & Cortina, 2017).

4.6.2 Feared Consequences to Reporting Sexual Assault or Obtaining Help

A number of students anticipated negative consequences, a result of reporting or obtaining help for sexual assault. Anticipated outcomes included, challenges in proving the assault occurred (34.4%), concerns the report may not be believed (28.5%), considered serious (53.6%), or remain confidential (19.4%) (Heywood et al., 2022, p.47). In previous studies, students had fears of being retraumatized, experiencing feelings of distress or anxiety, as well as disruptions to their social life (Holland & Cortina, 2017). Furthermore, students had concerns they or the offender would get into trouble (DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017), or that reporting their assault would be unhelpful (Holland & Cortina, 2017). Lastly, some students anticipated reporting or obtaining help would lead to negative consequences on studies or future career prospects (17.4%) (Heywood et al., 2022, p.47; Nisbet et al., 2022, p.26).

4.7 Minimising Sexual Assault and the Sexual Assault Myth

Another prominent theme revolved around students not always considering the incident significant enough to seek out university support. That is, especially if physical injuries or psychological harm were not involved (Holland & Cortina, 2017; DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017; Tarzia et al. 2024). This may be a result of the "rape myth," where culture depicts sexual assault in a misleading way. Due to sexual assault stereotypes, students may not identify their experience as sexual abuse and do not seek help as a result (DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017). Additionally, in a number of studies, students invalidated their own sexual assault experience by viewing it as an ordinary part of university culture (Holland & Cortina, 2017; DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017; Tarzia et al., 2024).

4.8.1 Findings

The present study was designed to identify what personal and environmental factors act as barriers to reporting and seeking support services, for female university students who experienced sexual assault in a university setting. The results of this study indicate that a number of barriers to reporting and help seeking exist. Students were often unaware of

where and how to make a formal report in a university setting (Nisbet et al., 2022, p.26; Heywood et al., 2022, p.47). They either did not know supports existed, or how these services or the reporting process could assist them (Nisbet et al., 2022, p.26; DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017). The university policies and processes were also identified as a barrier to accessing campus supports (Holland & Cortina, 2017). Students reported dissatisfaction with the formal sexual assault university reporting procedure, that included the guidance provided on how to make a report (Heywood et al., 2022, p.45). A lack of transparency in the reporting process, slow processing times, and no outcome to complaints made, were characteristics used to describe the university reporting process (Heywood et al., 2022, p.47; Nisbet et al., 2022, p. 37; Coote, 2022). Regarding support services for sexual assault, approximately 1 in 3 of students reported dissatisfaction (Heywood et al., 2022, p. 52), and identified student leaders and associated university staff in university accommodation unequipped to deal with reports of student sexual abuse (Nisbet et al., 2022, p.26). Feelings reported by students that developed as a result of sexual abuse, were also identified as barriers to reporting the sexual assault or seeking out help. Students commonly identified feelings of shame and embarrassment, with shame being the largest barrier to seeking help (Heywood et al., 2022, p.47). Furthermore, self-blame often impeded the seeking of support services, especially if alcohol was being consumed at the time of the abuse (DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017). Negative consequences, were also an anticipated outcome of reporting or seeking out assistance. Students expected the burden of being retraumatised, not being believed, experiencing social stigma, or even negative judgement. Additionally, some students had concerns their disclosure would not remain confidential or that there would be challenges in proving the assault occurred (Heywood et al., 2022, p.47; Holland and Cortina, 2017). Perhaps the most interesting finding is the concern that reporting the incident would lead to students getting into trouble or having negative consequences on future career prospects (Heywood et al., 2022, p.47). One unanticipated result, was student beliefs surrounding what constitutes sexual assault, where students often reduced the significance of their sexual assault experience, when comparing it to the sexual assault stereotype. Furthermore, they expressed it as an ordinary part of university culture (Holland & Cortina, 2017; DeLoveh & Cattaneo, 2017; Tarzia et al., 2024). Some of the issues emerging from these findings relate specifically to difficulties faced by students following sexual assault. To begin with, it must be recognised if sexual assault took place. Following this, if students decide to make a formal report, they may have difficulties navigating the university reporting and help seeking procedures. That is, while they potentially deal with negative emotions associated with sexual abuse. Furthermore, perceived consequences of reporting or seeking help can also act as barriers. These findings suggest reasons why students may choose not to report sexual assault or seek out help, and are at an increased risk of developing PTSD and associated occupational imbalance.

4.8.2 Recommendations

It is proposed that:

- Occupational Therapists collaborate with university staff, campus sexual assault support groups and students with lived experience, to tailor university sexual assault policies and procedures to student preferences (Heywood et al., 2022, p. 61).
- Occupational Therapists educate first year university students in lecture form. Information provided covers, acts that constitute sexual assault, sexual assault myths, common offenders, symptoms and feelings a result of sexual assault, social stigma and sexual assault, validating the sexual assault reporter, the importance of seeking help early in preventing PTSD, and what you can do if a peer discloses they have been sexually abused. This lecture is accessed either face-to-face, online, or as a recording, tailored to those at risk of re-traumatisation (Schell & Gillen, 2019, p. 422).
- Occupational Therapists provide information on university sexual assault reporting procedures and processes, sexual assault support services both external to and at the university campus, as well as the function of specific services (Schell & Gillen, 2019, p. 422).
- Occupational Therapists educate university employees in lecture form, guiding staff on what they are required to do to support students who disclose they have been sexually assaulted (Schell & Gillen, 2019, p. 422).

4.9 Conclusion

The purpose of this current study was to investigate the current perspectives on personal and environmental barriers to reporting and seeking support services, of females who have experienced sexual assault in a university setting. This study has identified a number of personal, cultural and systemic barriers to reporting and seeking support services. An implication of findings is that students who do not obtain the help they need are at a greater risk of developing PTSD, that can lead to occupational imbalance. The study here demonstrates that Occupational Therapists could have a role in collaborating with university staff and students to tailor sexual assault policies and procedures to the needs of university students. Furthermore, Occupational Therapists may be able to educate university students and staff about sexual assault, to fill gaps in knowledge, and address the importance of early help-seeking to support mental health outcomes and help prevent PTSD. Finally, Occupational Therapists could coach students on the university sexual assault reporting procedures and the function of sexual assault support services, both internal and external to the university. In doing this, the university community may be able to better support students in the help seeking process to assist in PTSD prevention and maintain occupational balance.

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